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TURNING AROUND AILING BUSINESS: 11 CASE STUDIES FROM INDIA

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Abstract

The Research Paper portrays exploratory analyses of certain recent successful and unsuccessful turnaround examples from the Indian business. The Paper aims to measure empirical relationships between the underpinning trends as evolved under eleven cases of successful turnaround vis-a-vis various stages of a turnaround management model namely. The model as propounded by world renowned turnaround website www.turnaround.org proposes sequential stages as; management change, situation analysis, emergency action, business re-organization and return to normalcy.

The cases adopted in this paper include Whirlpool, HUL, Aditya Birla Nuvo, CESC, Thermax, India Cements, Dabur, Shoppers Stop, Star India, Jain Irrigation Systems and Greaves Cotton.

Key Words: Turnaround, Innovation, strategy, Turnaround Management Model

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INTRODUCTION

Businessdictionary.com defined turnaround as “Positive, sustained reversal of hitherto prevailing negative conditions or performance of an economy, firm, industry, or market.” Periods of economic and financial distress pose special challenges to the capabilities and decision-making processes of most professional management teams. Not only do such occurrences increase demands on existing managerial abilities, but they also create a whole new spectrum of legal, accounting, and financial considerations that impact the renewal process. Today’s increased competition, cyclical and volatile financial markets, and economic trends have created a climate in which no business can take stability for granted. (www.turnaround.org)

Turnaround Model

Executives who encounter corporate distress often go through the same emotional stages as dying people: denial, anger, bargaining, depression, and finally acceptance. Corporate managers who recognize and acknowledge the signs of trouble in the earlier stages have a much better chance of a successful recovery for their corporation. Most businesses in distress display more than one of these external and internal signs of trouble: Ineffective Management Style, Overdiversification, Weak Financial Position, Poor Lender Relationships, Lack of Operating Controls, Market Lag, Explosive Growth, Precarious Customer Base, Family vs. Business Matters, and Operating without a Business Plan. (www.turnaround.org)

When we take a deep look into the process of turnaround of a business it appears to be far more complex as seen from periphery. Further complexities are added by the differing interests of different stakeholders of an ailing organization. The owners want to safeguard their stake and reputation. The Board of Directors is interested to play safe and avoid litigations. The investors want their capital back. The lending agencies want their money back with interest and so on.

Among the most potential causes of unsuccessful business, the majority may be credited to poor managerial decisions and actions. Major causes of business failure include; Autocratic Management, Poor Customer Services, Communication Failures, Ineffective Marketing

Strategies, Poor HR Policies and Practices, Decision-making without on the premise of objective research, Poor Compensation and Benefits Policies, Poor Financial Control and Management, Unclear Priorities, Goals and Responsibilities, Interrupted Supply chain, Mis-managed Growth and Expansion Unethical Conduct and Practices.

In order to bring about an effective turnaround it is mandatory that the real causes responsible for the problems are ascertained as accurately as possible. Logic suggests that the management may not suggest the 'true causes' because as if they were able to do so they would have already fixed those. The turnaround must be managed by some external experts. The external resources bring with them new insights and innovative approaches to view and interpret the situation with fresh paradigm. They also have ample experience and experience in managing turnaround. Under the guidance and control of the turnaround specialist the organizational restructuring takes place. Turnaround specialist is a preferred choice as compared to a turnaround consultant as turnaround specialist takes the entire control and management of the organization whereas turnaround consultant gives advice to the similar management which had already failed.

In turnaround process, a proper investigation must be done to find out the most ailing aspects of business and potential causal factors, find out strategic alternatives and the best action plans to implement, arrange funding for the initiatives, monitor the progress and take mid-term corrective actions as and when required.

Turnaround Management Model comprises the following stages: (www.turnaround.org)

- A. Changing the Management**
- B. Situation Analysis**
- C. Emergency Action**
- D. Business Restructuring**
- E. Return to Normal**

Management Change

The CEO Management must address the issues related to major stakeholder groups (executives, function managers, employees, lenders, vendors, customers, others). There must be change in the focus of how the company will operate to accomplish a turnaround. Most companies have a lack-of-sales problem, which necessitates a change to jump-start sales and drive revenue. There must be information that all can rely on for decision making. Production management must support and make what the market wants to purchase, at competitive price. You must nurture critical human capital resources that are left within the company, while at the same time holding them accountable for results.

Changing management is synonymous with changing the philosophy of how we will run the place to achieve results. Communication with all stakeholders is paramount through all stages of the process. Set goals that achieve stakeholder objectives, then apply incentive-based management to motivate the proper results. Tie everyone to the same broad set of goals and accent how functions can complement the performance of related departments.

Situation Analysis Stage

Your objective is to determine the severity of the situation and if it can be turned around. Answer questions like is the business viable? Can it survive? Should it be saved? Are there sufficient cash resources to fuel the turnaround? This analysis should culminate in formulating a preliminary action plan stating what is wrong, how to fix them, key strategies to turn the entity in a positive direction, and a cash flow forecast (at least 13 weeks) to understand cash usage.

Identify effective turnaround strategies. Operational strategies include increasing revenue, reducing costs, selling and redeploying assets, and competitive repositioning. Strategic initiatives include adopting sound corporate and business strategies and tactics, setting specific goals and objectives that align with the ultimate goals of the stakeholders. Too often, goals are misaligned with the ultimate direction and cause confusion, wasted time, false-starts, and send employees in the wrong direction. Understand that many of the good employees have already left the

company, you will have to work with the second string in the essence of time and build as you go.

You must understand the life cycle of the business and how it relates to the chosen turnaround strategy. Document key issues so that all will understand what you are trying to accomplish, and all will pull in the same direction. Identify what product and business segments are most profitable, particularly at the gross margin level, and eliminate weak and nonperformers. Make certain that all functional areas (sales, production) are working to support the goals of their counterparts. Selling work with flexible delivery times can fill valleys in production cycles, which reduce costs per unit. Producing only what sales can sell to meet customer demand will increase sales and gross margin.

Turnaround strategies are often impacted by local government policy considerations and regulations. In the United States the WARN Act requires 60 day notice of massive lay-offs, which certainly impacts cash flow. In many countries in Europe and Far East there are stringent rules (local country driven) governing the payment of wages after lay-offs, dealing with the local authorities regarding the process, and even prioritizing which workers can be laid off when in fact others may be more qualified. When government policy favors labor and employment is not “at will” there will be complications to the process.

Emergency Action Stage

Your objective is to gain control of the situation, particularly the cash, and establish breakeven. Centralize the cash management function to ensure control. If you stop the cash bleed, you enable the entity to survive. Time is your enemy. Protect asset value by demonstrating that the business is viable and in transition.

You must raise cash immediately. Review the balance sheet for internal sources of cash such as collecting accounts receivable, and renegotiating payments against accounts payable. Sell unprofitable business units, real estate, unutilized assets. Secure asset-based loans if needed. Restructure debt to balance the amount of interest payments with the level the company can afford. Lay off employees quickly and fairly. It is much better to cut deep all at once, than to make small cuts repeatedly. Remaining employees are more prone to focus if they believe in job security, rather than look for the next action.

Rightsizing the company is much more than employee layoffs. Correct under pricing of products, prune product lines to only those profitable and that meet demand, and weed out weak and problem customers. Sometimes there is too much overhead applied to support a customer who isn't paying their fair share of that service. Emphasize selling more product at profitable rates. Reward those that change the situation, sanction or release those that don't.

Business Restructuring Stage

Your objective is to create profitability through remaining operations. Stress product line pricing and profitability. Restructure the business for increased profitability and return on assets and investments. At this stage your focus should change from cash flow crisis to profitability. Fix the capital structure and renegotiate the long and short term debt.

Ensure that reporting systems put in place are operationalized to show profitability at each revenue center, cost center, profit center, cash center, and incentive center. Unless employees can see it they can't manage it.

Incentive-based management will drive employees to get involved smartly, and manage to the goals all ascribe to. Create teams of employees to identify and rework inefficiencies and promote profitability.

There are only two ways to increase sales. Sell existing product to new customers. Sell new products to existing customers. Do both if you want growth.

Return to Normal Stage

Your objective is to institutionalize the changes in corporate culture to emphasize profitability, ROI, and return on assets employed. Seek opportunities for profitable growth. Build on competitive strengths. Improve customer service and relationships. Build continuous management and employee training and development programs to raise the caliber of your human capital.

This could be a time to restructure long term financing at more reasonable rates now that the company is stable and on a path to growth.

The odds of a successful turnaround are increased dramatically if a Turnaround Process Phases and Actions Plan is implemented and followed. This plan can certainly be adapted to unique situations when required.

CASE STUDIES

Case 1: Whirlpool

- a) **Management Change:** Yes, the management took place, at the time when the company was struggling with gradually weakening financial health, losing its customers; Mr. Arvind Uppal took the command as the President (Asia-Pacific) in the year 2005 and initiated turnaround.
- b) **Situation Analysis:** Failure to swiftly respond to emerging competitors, local as well as global. Low Morale due to losses, personnel engaged in cross-purposes leading to counter productivity.
- c) **Emergency Action:** Boost-up the morale of the people and create a winning team pulling the company to a common goal. War-time: Minimize exposure and risks; Peace-times: Expose and Take risks.
- d) **Business Restructuring:** Get disengaged from irrelevant distractions such as overt attention to competitors and focus on key organizational strengths such as people and product innovation. Customer Focus, offering them a wide choice. Focus on core product line such as home appliances (refrigerators, washing machines, microwaves and air conditioners. Focus on key clientele (women) and introduction of new products meeting their needs like water solutions and high-end kitchen solutions.
- e) **Return to Normal:** The Company has turned around and has the best profitability margins in the industry.

Case 2: Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL)

- a) **Management Change:** Yes, Nitin Paranjpe took over as MD & CEO in 2008.

- b) **Situation Analysis:** Causal Factors: lack of Quick responsiveness to market Change and Volatility,
- c) **Emergency Action:** needed to respond with speed and agility Over the last few years we have dramatically improved our 'go to market' execution both through discontinuous expansion in our reach and by leveraging technology to improve its quality. Simultaneously, we have been ruthless on costs. We are constantly asking ourselves how we can strip out every rupee that the consumer is not willing to pay for. It is this approach to cost that has generated the "fuel" for growth and enabled us to invest in product quality and superior benefits, thereby increasing the competitiveness of our brands. These are the sorts of actions that have helped us manage challenges and emerge stronger.
- d) **Business Restructuring:** shorter planning cycles, investment in processes and technology, and initiatives like Sunset, which promote a bias for action. Through Sunset, any unresolved actions are automatically escalated to the management at the highest levels and resolved quickly. People within the organization feel good when they see their feedback being acted upon promptly. customer centricity
- e) **Return to Normal:** encouraged all our employees to spend time engaging with consumers and customers to understand their needs and address their complaints. It is this single-minded focus on the consumer that has helped our brands deliver better consumer-value.

Case 3: Aditya Birla Nuvo

- a) **Management Change:** No Mahendra Mohan Gupta, CMD
- b) **Situation Analysis:** The financial year 2008/09 was marked by the advent of a worldwide economic recession in tandem with a liquidity and credit crisis. This spilled into 2009/10 and slowed the growth momentum. The crisis affected [Aditya Birla Nuvo's \(ABNL\) profitability](#). We had invested

over Rs 800 crore to fund growth in the life insurance business and for the acquisition of the retail broking outfit. Expansion of stores in the Fashion and Lifestyle business also impaired profitability. Our export oriented IT-ITeS and apparel contract manufacturing businesses were hit. Subsequently, we reported a consolidated net loss of Rs 436 crore in 2008/09 against a profit of Rs 151 crore the previous year. Investments and working capital requirements strained ABNL's standalone balance sheet, with net debt-EBITDA reaching 5.8, and gross debt touching Rs 4,500 crore. Cash conservation was a big challenge.

- c) **Emergency Action:** To tackle the situation, we took a number of proactive cost rationalization initiatives across our businesses. Cash generation by manufacturing businesses and capital infusion of Rs 1,000 crore by our promoters helped de-leverage the balance sheet and reduce the interest burden. These measures also ensured availability of growth capital, enabling our businesses to outperform the industry even in an extremely challenging environment
- d) **Business Restructuring:** Garments subsidiaries were merged into the company for optimisation of costs and resources and to derive synergies. Innovative structuring of debt instruments helped pare the interest outgo in our subsidiaries. The results are evident. Today, all of our businesses are profitable and growing. Led by strong growth in renewal premium, Birla Sun Life Insurance has turned profitable. Once a capital guzzler, the financial services business has become the largest contributor to ABNL's profitability. Today, Aditya Birla Financial Services is the fifth-largest fund manager in India, excluding banks and LIC.
- e) **Return to Normal:** The Fashion and Lifestyle and IT-ITeS businesses have turned profitable. Our manufacturing businesses continue to yield strong cash flows. Aditya Birla Minacs, the IT-ITeS arm, crossed the Rs 2,000 crore revenue mark in 2011/12. And despite the regulatory challenges surrounding the sector, our telecom business - [Idea Cellular](#) - has been the biggest revenue share gainer in the past two years. All our businesses are today well placed and contributing to

growth. Today, ABNL is generating 50 per cent more revenue than in 2008/09. EBITDA has grown almost four times. Net profit has risen multifold. Standalone net-debt/equity at 0.66 and net debt/EBITDA, at 3.6, are quite reasonable considering that 60 per cent of capital employed is deployed in longterm investments.

Case 4: CESC

- a) **Management Change:** Yes, Sanjeev Goenka took over as VP
- b) **Situation Analysis:** The [transformation of CESC](#), responsible for Kolkata's power supply, into one of India's best-run power utilities, is a remarkable story of a [company reinventing itself](#) . By 1989, when the Goenka association with CESC began, Calcutta, as it was known then, had earned the dubious distinction of being India's "load shedding city". Domestic and industrial consumers lived without power for 10 hours a day, and the problem was aggravated by power theft. There had been no worthwhile addition to CESC's generating capacity, a large part of which was half a century old. The lack luster balance sheet provided no joy to investors. And the state government refused to revise tariffs or delayed revisions. Meanwhile, fuel and operational costs continued to rise. Over the years, the state government passed the increasing cost burden to CESC's industrial consumers, which meant an alarming rise in cross-subsidies. The government had different and conflicting interests. Its electricity board supplied CESC, competed with it, and also played the role of the tariff regulator. This led to disallowance of CESC's legitimate tariff claims, almost forcing its business to become non-viable. CESC had no other option but to take legal recourse. This route was time consuming and the company also had to face government-appointed committees to examine issues relating to fuel surcharge. By 1999, the West Bengal Electricity Regulatory Commission was constituted. It had judicial powers to determine tariffs. But even after the notification of the commission, there was no tariff revision for two years. Costs remained unrecovered and for the first time in its history, CESC went into the red - the company's net worth was wiped out.

- c) **Emergency Action:** In a landmark judgment in October 2002, the Supreme Court upheld the claims made by CESC. With this, the utility eventually came back from the brink. In the meantime, the company set up a 500 MW (two units of 250 MW each) generating plant at Budge Budge. A third unit was added in 2010.
- d) **Business Restructuring:** Today, Budge Budge is one of India's most efficient thermal power plants. The overall combined availability of CESC's power plants was about 95 per cent in 2011/12 and the three generating stations are among the top 10 in the country. Transmission and distribution losses are now among the lowest. By the end of 2011/12, there was no load shedding in Kolkata for want of supply despite the substantial rise in peak demand.
- e) **Return to Normal:** CESC, which had a debt equity ratio of 5.4:1 a decade ago, has improved its position remarkably and the ratio now stands at 0.6. The company added 100,000 new customers last year and the average time taken to provide new connections has come down to 18 days from 28. It is now ready to add generating capacity, invest in improving distribution efficiency and increase the overall quality of its services.

Case 5: Shoppers Stop

- a) **Management Change:** Yes, Managing Director Govind Shrikhande
- b) **Situation Analysis:** The slowdown in demand in India came out of the [trillion-dollar meltdown in the US](#) and Europe. It gathered momentum over two quarters, with the health scare in Mumbai and Pune, the stock market crash, the Telangana protests in Hyderabad, and then 26/11 in Mumbai.

All these shocks came one after the other. IT, exports and banking were hit the worst. Our [like-for-like sales growth](#) turned negative in the second half of

financial year 2009, and continued to remain so till April-June in financial year 2010. It was a great test of the industry and its fundamentals. [Retail thrives](#) in a growing economy, when incomes are on the rise and consumers have great hopes about the future. When consumer sentiment turns negative due to job losses or a drop in income, spending is either skipped or postponed.

- c) **Emergency Action:** Only then will they continue to shop with you. Quite unlike what most companies do in such times, we repositioned our brand and launched a new logo. When a slowdown hits, everyone is affected. You require the support of everyone in the ecosystem, whether you are running at a profit or a loss. Everyone understands that running a business is like running a marathon and not a 100 metre sprint. So, during the 2008 slowdown, senior associates accepted salary cuts, others waived increments and suppliers chipped in with extra credit. We also learnt that it is essential to evaluate businesses. Businesses/formats/stores that are never going to be profitable need to be closed. Postponing this can only cause more harm. In some cases the customer may not be ready, or your scale may not support profitability. So, closing the business without any emotional baggage is a prudent decision to sustain the overall business. We closed down Arcelia and Brio, two new formats, at that time. We right-sized a few stores, including our department stores in Bandra (Mumbai) and MGF Saket (Delhi). And our manpower costs were trimmed by around 12 per cent.
- d) **Business Restructuring:** When spending is postponed, retail is impacted, especially the clothing and accessory categories. This directly results in a drop in like-for-like sales, impacting profitability and growth. The retail sector saw the death of several players in this period, and a number of others had to re-strategise their formats and balance sheets. It was a great time for learning. Our board challenged us to create a recession proof model that could face slowdowns. One of our chief learning from the slowdown was to never compromise on customer experience. Customers should continue to get your best service and merchandise. Even finance ministers can't predict what will happen to the economy. So, get full control on controllable, as uncontrollable are not in your hand. Every business has

certain fixed variable costs. Some of the costs and factors impacting business are never going to be in the control of a company. For example, economic growth, oil prices or stock indices are not in the control of any single company. There is no point in sweating when these factors become negative. Identifying the controllable costs, such as energy and employees, and gaining full control over them helps the business focus its energies on the right metrics. We were able to cut power consumption costs by more than 25 per cent over a 15-month period.

- e) **Return to Normal:** Another important thing during the slowdown is to communicate. When the sky starts falling, everybody notices it. But if one communicates steps that are being taken and the rationale behind them to everyone, fear gets converted into target-oriented objectives. We communicated issues very clearly across the organisation and had all our stakeholders rallying behind us completely.

Case 6: Thermax

- a) **Management Change:** Anu Aga, Founder & Chairperson along with external Turnaround specialist agency
- b) **Situation Analysis:** In the late 1990s, [Thermax](#) had got used to what the late Sumantra Ghoshal called "satisfactory underperformance". In turning it around, the most difficult and yet the most important move was to change the mindset and the culture of the company. We had to move away from our comfort zone, stop blaming external circumstances for poor performance, and assume full responsibility.
- c) **Emergency Action:** The immediate trigger for the change was an anonymous letter I received from a shareholder blaming me for my inaction. I had thought that poor performance mainly affected me and my family, the majority shareholders. Suddenly, I realised that as a public limited company we had to

protect the interests of the 40-odd per cent shareholders who had placed their faith in Thermax. I was convinced that our management was out of its depth and needed outside help. My senior executives resisted the idea. Most men find it difficult to seek help because I think it comes in the way of their 'macho image'. The board decided to hire a consulting company.

- d) **Business Restructuring:** Our turnaround focused on divesting non-core businesses. We restructured into six core businesses in the areas of energy and environment. By downsizing and improving our operational efficiency, we were able to bring down our employee cost from 16 per cent of turnover to less than 7.5 per cent, on a larger sales base. We also brought in a performance culture.

We reconstituted our board to bring in more independent directors. The promoter members stepped down from executive positions, and operational aspects were left to a nonfamily professional team led by the managing director.

- e) **Return to Normal:** After achieving a financial turnaround, we set an ambitious growth target. This programme - since then achieved by my successor and team - was based on operational excellence, a streamlined organisational structure, and rekindling innovation in a disciplined and systematic manner.

Case 7: India Cements

- a) **Management Change:** N. Srinivasan, [Vice Chairman & MD](#)
- b) **Situation Analysis:** In the mid-1990s, with a capacity of just 2.6 million tonnes, [India Cements](#) risked becoming an also-ran. That set us thinking and we decided to become a large regional player in the South. Between 1997 and 1998 we acquired Visaka Cements and Cement Corporation of India's Yerraguntla unit (both in Andhra Pradesh) through competitive bidding. In June 1998 we took over Raasi Cements (also in AP) through a hostile acquisition. Simultaneously, we also set up a new plant at Dalavoi, Tamil Nadu. In less than two years, our capacity

had catapulted to nine million tonnes. The acquisitions cost us Rs 1,600 crore and were predominantly funded by debt. What we did not anticipate was the rush by other cement companies in the region to set up capacities when the government withdrew all sales tax-related incentives.

c) **Emergency Action:** Without these incentives no cement plant was viable at the cement prices prevailing then. Capacity as much as 40 per cent of demand was added. Naturally, this sent prices crashing. At one point a truckload of sand cost more than a truckload of cement in parts of AP. We began to incur losses and our ability to service the Rs 1,750 crore debt in our books suffered. We defaulted and lenders began harassing us. Such was the condition that we had to curtail production due to lack of working capital. We sold Vishnu Cements, which we acquired along with Raasi Cements, hoping it would ease pressure. But that was not enough. We realised we were in a hole and opted for a corporate debt restructuring (CDR) scheme, which came into effect from January 2003. The CDR bought us time to focus on operations. We shed manpower (about 1,000 employees), cut production costs, sold our ships and some land.

d) **Business Restructuring:** Extraordinary situations demand extraordinary measures. So, in September 2005, we made an audacious move, coming out with a Global Depository Receipts issue while still in the CDR scheme.

Many warned us that it was an unwise thing to do. Investors would not even look at a company that had defaulted on its debt obligations, they warned. But we went ahead and raised Rs 477 crore, which was used to pay off some debt. That was the turning point.

e) **Return to Normal:** Soon cement prices began to improve and this accelerated our revival. In the following years, we raised more funds from the market to fund our growth plans. Today our capacity stands at 15.5 million tonnes and we have expanded to North India as well. The crisis that set us back by a few years taught

me one thing - never expand in a fractured market using debt. When you have no control over prices, your ability to service debt will be impaired.

Case 8: Star Plus

- a) **Management Change:** Peter Mukerjea
- b) **Situation Analysis:** Star launched in India in 1992. The [STAR Plus](#) that you see today was born out of the changing media landscape in India. In the early years, STAR was unable to provide any localised programming because of an agreement with [Subhash Chandra](#)'s Zee TV. The agreement was a big roadblock as it prevented STAR Plus from becoming a Hindi channel. [Both channels were beamed into India through the AsiaSat transponder, owned by Chandra's Asia Today, in which STAR had a stake. Their contract stated that STAR would concentrate on providing only English content.] We tried dubbed Hindi programming but realised it was not the solution. Around 1996, the relationship between STAR and Zee soured, and in 1999 the ties between the two companies ended completely (Chandra bought out STAR's stake in AsiaSat). This marked the advent of STAR Plus as a 24-hour Hindi channel.
- c) **Emergency Action:** The management initially chose to go down a certain path, acquiring Doordarshan's library of programmes and having reruns on STAR Plus. But the audiences were so different that the programmes did not gel with the channel, though they did lift STAR Plus's performance slightly.
- d) **Business Restructuring:** When I took over as the CEO around 2000, we realised that we needed to change the rules of the game. We needed to be up there with Zee. We were driven by the belief that if Zee could do it, we could too. We only needed to think it through, make the right investments and get the right

programming. Whilst in this process, we came across Who Wants to be a Millionaire, which was a big hit across Europe. However, we could not run it as an English show as we were now a 24-hour Hindi channel. But, the same show in Hindi? To be honest we were not sure if it would work until we put it on air as Kaun Banega Crorepati (KBC), with Amitabh Bachchan as the host. The show was received well and delivered good results. It was a combination of good programming, a big Bollywood star, right scheduling and good telecast timing. To achieve all this we had to take a major decision: to pull out our cash cow, the 9 p.m. English news produced by NDTV, and replacing it with KBC. It was a big gamble and it paid off well.

- e) **Return to Normal:** The key lesson we learnt was that viewers, not programmers, had to be central to the programming strategy. Another lesson was that we had to provide content to viewers in Hindi and other regional languages - being only an English language broadcaster was not good enough. The same learning was used when launching STAR News, after the split with NDTV. We pulled out a successful news show and replaced it with something untested before on Indian television. The strategy worked. We challenged orthodoxy, took big risks, made shows like KBC with a big host, big prize money and great production values along with few other soaps. And we attracted viewers.

Case 9: Jain Irrigation Systems

- a) **Management Change:** Bhavarlal H. Jain & Aqua International Partners
- b) **Situation Analysis:** The apology, a half-page advertisement by [Jain Irrigation Systems](#) in The Economic Times, on November 26, 1997, began thus: "I'm sad that for the first time since our inception, we've fared badly. We ventured into 'unknown' areas like finance, IT and granite at the cost of our core business... We have lost money but more importantly, we've lost some of our reputation. I feel it's my duty to account for, to own up, to admit my misjudgements, to apologise."

Not many in the management team agreed with my decision to apologise but nevertheless I went ahead to cleanse my conscience. The 1990s offered new-found opportunities, and being a dream merchant, I could not resist the temptation of taking advantage of them to become a large conglomerate. Between 1992 and 1994 we acquired an IT company, took a granite quarry on lease, ventured into merchant banking and even bought an advertising agency. These diversifications happened along with forward/backward integration projects for our existing operations. By March 1997, we were trying to manage 11 different projects involving an investment of Rs 400 crore - almost equal to the company's size then. About Rs 250 crore was raised by way of debt.

c) **Emergency Action:** All the diversifications were conceived on instinct and in the euphoria that surrounded the economy then. But the organisation lacked management bandwidth. The investments turned bad, leading to diversion of working capital, which hurt our core businesses. We posted losses. The share prices, which had touched Rs 365 (on a face value of Rs 10) in February 1994, crashed to a low Rs 8 in October 2000. Lenders hauled us to court and a few even sought our liquidation. We were struggling to breathe. In early 2001, Aqua International Partners, a water-specific boutique fund, offered to invest in the company. There was a catch: we had to give the fund a controlling stake. We grappled with the unenviable question: who should survive, the promoter or the company? We decided to cede control, and in August 2002, the fund invested Rs 183 crore and took a 49.4 per cent stake in the company. The promoters' stake dropped from 73 per cent to less than 37 per cent and two family members had to vacate the Board.

d) **Business Restructuring:** We used the money to retire debt and bolster our working capital needs. We exited non-core businesses. By 2005, the company had revived and its share price was at Rs 160. The fund chose to exit.

- e) **Return to Normal:** Today we are a Rs 3,800 crore company, the largest globally in mango processing and tissue culture, and second largest in drip irrigation. The share price is hovering around Rs 80 (on a face value of Rs 2 per share). Diversifying into unknown areas without required management bandwidth and eyeing disproportionate growth using debt is not sustainable.

Case 10: Greaves Cotton

- a) **Management Change:** Sunil Pahilajani, MD & CEO
- b) **Situation Analysis:** Ours is a company with a rich heritage of more than 150 years of engineering transformation in India. [Greaves](#) has demonstrated perseverance, resilience and the ability to respond to a crisis. One such situation was at the turn of this century, when the business was not in the best of shape. More than half its peak net worth during the four preceding years had been eroded. Interest outgo stood at an all-time high. High production and manpower costs had reduced competitiveness. The company had symptoms of potential sickness. Greaves incurred a loss of Rs 92.61 crore in the financial year 2000/01, which was extended for 18 months.
- c) **Emergency Action:** To overcome the situation, the management decided on a two-pronged restructuring exercise, in terms of business and finance. The business restructuring exercise, which ran through the critical period of 2000 to 2004, had a two-fold objective. The first was to focus on core businesses and exit from non-core ventures (such as the tie-up with SAME Group for tractors and engines), and suspend lossmaking units such as Rajasthan Polymers & Resins Ltd and eventually sell them off. The company also sought to liquidate overseas subsidiaries, rationalise them and divest its stake in companies such as Piaggio Vehicles Pvt Ltd. The second part of the objective was to reduce operating

expenses.

- d) **Business Restructuring:** Financial restructuring was undertaken during the same period. It resulted in enhanced cash flow and a stronger balance sheet. This included monetising a major portion of its shareholding in [Crompton Greaves](#), the sale of surplus real estate, commercial property and non-core investments, and most importantly switching from the strategy of stock push to demand pull. All this reduced receivables by 44 per cent.
- e) **Return to Normal:** In other words, Greaves strengthened profitability through strategic initiatives that were carried out across the organisation. The focus was on engines and applications, and the infrastructure segment where our expertise lay. Migration from manual systems to automation led to increased efficiency at lower cost. It also enabled us to adopt modern manufacturing practices such as Lean, Total Quality Management and Total Productive Maintenance, which increased productivity. We invested in R&D to meet stringent emission norms, and explored development of futuristic products.

The results of this major exercise were seen in the next few years. In 2003/04, the operating profit or EBIDTA was Rs 87.47 crore and profit after tax was Rs 21.73 crore. The interest outgo declined 17.53 per cent, compared to 2002/03. This transformation was not confined merely to numbers. The way we did business changed. The exercise addressed myriad challenges such as cost reduction, increasing efficiency and improving margins, but all of this could be simplified into one single word: focus. Today, Greaves Cotton* has transformed itself into an Rs 1,800 crore, multi-product engineering company. This is largely due to our increased focus. Greaves has embarked on a journey of profitability and sustained growth. It is eyeing product portfolio expansion and new customer acquisition. The lessons learnt helped it withstand the economic crisis of 2008.

Case 11: Dabur India

- a) **Management Change:** Sunil Duggal, CEO
- b) **Situation Analysis:** The start of the new millennium, the year 2000, brought new challenges for Dabur. Industry overall witnessed a downturn, with demand hitting a new low, but the [fast-moving consumer goods](#) (FMCG) industry was somewhat insulated from the crisis and reported good growth. For Dabur, however, those were trying times. A decade into liberalisation, the FMCG industry saw competition intensify, with deep-pocketed multinational companies (MNCs) trying every trick in the book to capture market share. The demand for consumer products was rising. But [Dabur](#) - despite strong brand recall and trust - was having trouble cashing in. That is when we decided to go for a course correction and implement measures that not only changed how people saw Dabur, but also put the company firmly on the growth track.
- c) **Emergency Action:** A thorough check of our business was undertaken, and the core group decided on a multipronged growth strategy. As the first step, we decided to outsource non-core businesses like IT, and to concentrate on making quality consumer products. Simultaneously, we decided to refurbish our product portfolio and enter several emerging and sunrise categories such as skin care, packaged fruit juice and toothpaste. The packaging of our entire [portfolio](#) was refurbished to put it in sync with the needs and aspirations of the 21st century consumer. In addition, we drew up a rapid expansion plan which also included taking the inorganic route to grow business. We recognised - much ahead of the competition - that rural India would become a key growth driver. A blueprint was chalked out to target this consumer class and widen our distribution footprint in the hinterland, a move that is paying dividends even today.

- d) **Business Restructuring:** While launching new products and upgrading packaging to remain contemporary, I felt it was also time to expand our horizons and took on the MNCS on their home turf and in overseas markets. This was a big game-changer for Dabur. Before 2000, Dabur's overseas business was limited to exporting a limited number of products for the Indian diaspora in select markets. We felt there was a larger market beyond the diaspora. If we had to reach those consumers, we would have to be based close to their homes. The small overseas business we had established earlier had given us a good understanding of the consumers in these markets. So we set out to create products specifically for them.

As a first step, we decided to establish a manufacturing facility abroad, rather than ship products from India, as that would make us more nimble in addressing the changing needs of consumers, and provide us a leaner and quicker supply chain. This decision paid off - our products soon became favourites with Arab consumers, and our international business became a strong growth engine for the company, helping it tide over the recession, when it hit the domestic market.

- e) **Return to Normal:** After targeting the West Asian market, we expanded our overseas business further by venturing into sub-Saharan Africa and nearby markets like Turkey. Today, our overseas business accounts for nearly 30 per cent of consolidated turnover. Another measure of our international success is that our premium skin and hair care brand, Vatika, is probably the only Indian FMCG brand to report equal turnover from both Indian and overseas sales. Today, Dabur is viewed by consumers and investors as a true Indian multinational. During the past few years the businesses around the world have experienced, either directly or indirectly, turmoil like downsizing, serial recessions, mergers, acquisitions, hostile takeovers, imperatives like business process reengineering, and organizational restructuring. There have been a large number of instances

when businesses went sick and ultimately met with closure, bankruptcy, thus causing great agonies to investors, lenders, employees, owners and customers.

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